

OPTI-FAB: Latency-First Stream-Aware Inference with Confidence-Gated Early Exit for Real-Time Wafer Defect Classification

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Abstract—Automated visual inspection of semiconductor wafers using deep neural networks is critical for modern fab yield management. However, traditional deployment pipelines process images in a serialized capture-save-load-infer loop. Our profiling confirms that 63.9% of the end-to-end pipeline latency is spent on file I/O, OS buffering, and memory transfers. This latency bottleneck makes inline wafer rejection at transport speeds (e.g., 100 mm/s) practically unfeasible. In this work, we present OPTI-FAB, a latency-first framework that reframes wafer inspection as a streaming-systems problem on a Laptop GPU. OPTI-FAB processes inspection data as a continuous pixel stream using a circular sliding-window buffer, overlapping acquisition with inference. We introduce a confidence-gated decision mechanism utilizing normalized Shannon entropy to trigger early exits, allowing defect classification before full-frame capture. For borderline cases, we implement a dual-path architecture that routes uncertain frames out-of-band to a sequential Monte Carlo (MC) Dropout pipeline for epistemic uncertainty estimation. Optimized with TensorRT FP16, our model achieves a mean inference latency of 0.79 ms on an NVIDIA RTX 4050 Laptop GPU, enabling a 63.9% reduction in mean end-to-end pipeline latency (3.00 ms vs. 8.30 ms), with median latency of 2.47 ms satisfying the 3.0 ms inline rejection budget under nominal GPU scheduling conditions. OPTI-FAB achieves 91% classification accuracy on full-frame images and 53.3% accuracy under live streaming early-exit conditions (at 92.0% early-exit rate, mean scan completion 59.7%), demonstrating proof-of-concept feasibility for inline quality control at wafer transport speeds. Closing the gap between full-frame and streaming accuracy via partial-frame training augmentation is identified as the primary direction for future work.

Index Terms—Wafer inspection, Laptop GPU, Streaming inference, TensorRT, Early exit, Uncertainty estimation

I. INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor manufacturing requires rapid, high-precision quality control to minimize yield loss. Wafer surface defect inspection, historically performed manually or via classical rule-based computer vision, has increasingly transitioned to deep learning-based object detection and classification models [1], [2]. Despite the high accuracy of these modern convolutional networks, their practical integration into production lines is often limited by strict system latency constraints.

Wafer transportation systems typically move wafers under scanning line-scan cameras at speeds of 100 mm/s or higher. To achieve true inline rejection—where a defective wafer is caught and diverted before exiting the inspection zone—the

classification pipeline must complete within a tight window of a few milliseconds.

Traditional visual inspection setups utilize a serialized processing pipeline:

Capture → Buffer → Save File → OS I/O → Load → Infer → Decide (1)

Our system-level profiling confirms that 63.9% of the end-to-end latency in this pipeline is spent outside the neural network, as corroborated by the profiling results of Li et al. [3]. Overhead is dominated by local storage writes, operating system file caches, disk I/O, and GPU host-to-device memory copies. Optimizing model weights or pruning channels alone cannot address this I/O bottleneck.

In this paper, we propose **OPTI-FAB**, a latency-first inspection system designed to bypass file-system serialization entirely. OPTI-FAB treats visual inspection as a continuous pixel stream:

Camera Stream → Circular Buffer ↔ Inference → Gate → Decide (2)

By maintaining a circular sliding-window buffer, OPTI-FAB overlaps pixel ingestion with Laptop GPU inference. Crucially, rather than waiting for a full frame to be scanned and saved, OPTI-FAB runs inference on partially filled frames. Using a confidence-gated early exit, the system makes deterministic classification decisions once cumulative confidence exceeds a calculated threshold (typically at 50% to 68% of frame scanning completion). This concept builds upon early-exit network topologies [4], [5] and adaptive experts [6], [7], extending them to raw pixel streams.

To ensure robustness, OPTI-FAB incorporates a dual-path inference design. High-confidence deterministic predictions are routed through an ultra-fast TensorRT FP16 path. Borderline or noisy inputs are analyzed using sequential Monte Carlo (MC) Dropout on a Keras backend to estimate epistemic uncertainty, allowing the system to flag highly uncertain wafers for manual operator review instead of risking false accepts.

II. RELATED WORK

Automated surface inspection in semiconductor manufacturing has progressed from traditional template matching and thresholding to deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

Recent survey work by Luan et al. [1] summarizes CNN architectures applied to wafer defect patterns, typically highlighting offline visual classification. For inline applications, Zhao et al. [2] proposed YOLOv8-based defect detection. However, these methods assume full-frame availability, ignoring streaming latency.

To reduce inference times under tight computational budgets, early-exit networks have been introduced. Works such as BranchyNet [4] and surveys by Rahmath et al. [5] demonstrate that easy-to-classify samples can exit early at intermediate layers, reducing execution costs. Similarly, in concurrent work, Mokssit et al. [7] propose adaptive confidence gating, while multi-exit experts (e.g., BEEM [6]) route inputs dynamically based on output confidence.

Uncertainty estimation via Monte Carlo (MC) Dropout, proposed by Gal and Ghahramani [8], has been widely adopted to gauge epistemic uncertainty in deep networks. In industrial contexts, Li et al. [3] explored edge AI for fault detection, yet literature lacks the integration of sliding-window row streams with gated early exit and MC Dropout. OPTI-FAB fills this gap.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Problem Formulation and Latency Budget

Given a wafer transport mechanism operating at a constant velocity $v = 100$ mm/s and a physical tolerance window $d = 0.3$ mm for inline mechanical rejection gates, the maximum allowable end-to-end latency budget T_{budget} is defined as:

$$T_{\text{budget}} = \frac{d}{v} = 3.0 \text{ ms} \quad (3)$$

If the pipeline latency exceeds 3.0 ms, the wafer will have traveled past the physical rejection mechanism, making inline sorting impossible.

B. Circular Buffer Sliding-Window

A camera scanner feeds grayscale pixel rows line-by-line. OPTI-FAB maintains a fixed-size circular ring buffer $B \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H \times 1}$, where $H = W = 160$ pixels. As new rows are scanned at a hardware scan speed $S = 10$ rows per clock tick, the buffer B_t is updated by rolling old rows and stacking the newly ingested row block $I_t \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times W \times 1}$:

$$B_t = \begin{bmatrix} B_{t-1}[S :, :, :] \\ I_t \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The buffer is zeroed upon detection of a wafer transition event (rising edge of transport sensor), ensuring no inter-wafer pixel contamination. Inference is blocked until the buffer is at least 50% filled (representing the scanning of 80 rows) to ensure minimum visual context.

C. Model Architecture and Grayscale Adapter

We deploy a MobileNetV2 backbone [9] pretrained on ImageNet [10] as our feature extractor. A learned 1×1 projection is preferred over naive channel repetition as it

allows the adapter to learn a class-discriminative pseudo-color mapping during fine-tuning:

$$X_{\text{RGB}} = \text{Conv2D}_{1 \times 1}(X_{\text{Gray}}, \text{filters} = 3) \quad (5)$$

The base model features are pooled via Global Average Pooling and passed through a Dense layer with 256 units, a Dropout layer ($r = 0.4$), and a Softmax output layer mapping to 8 wafer defect classes: *clean*, *crack*, *edge_defect*, *open*, *other*, *scratch*, *short*, and *spot*.

During training, we freeze the first 100 layers of the MobileNetV2 base and fine-tune the remaining layers using the Adam optimizer [11] ($lr = 1 \times 10^{-4}$) under a balanced class weight loss function. Class weights are computed as $w_i = N/(K \times n_i)$, where N is total samples, K is number of classes, and n_i is samples in class i . Training augmentation included random horizontal/vertical flips, $\pm 15^\circ$ rotation, and $\pm 10\%$ brightness jitter.

D. Confidence-Gated Early Exit and Entropy

For every tick after the buffer is 50% full, the system runs inference on the current buffer state. Let $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_K]$ be the softmax output vector over $K = 8$ classes. The predicted class is $c^* = \arg \max P$, and the confidence is p_{c^*} . We measure uncertainty using normalized Shannon entropy H :

$$H = -\frac{1}{\ln K} \sum_{i=1}^K p_i \ln(p_i + \epsilon) \quad (6)$$

where $\epsilon = 1 \times 10^{-9}$. The decision logic at each tick is governed by the following rules:

- If $p_{c^*} \geq 0.98$ and $H \leq 0.05$:
 - If $c^* \neq \text{clean} \rightarrow$ **REJECT** (Early exit)
 - If $c^* = \text{clean} \rightarrow$ continue scanning (ACCEPT is only allowed at 100% scan to avoid missing defects in unscanned regions)
- If $p_{c^*} \geq 0.98$ and $H > 0.05 \rightarrow$ **DEFER** for manual review
- If $p_{c^*} < 0.98 \rightarrow$ **CONTINUE** scanning next rows

E. Monte Carlo (MC) Dropout Uncertainty Path

For borderline cases where the fast path output triggers a deferral, the system switches to the MC Dropout path [8]. To obtain stochastic predictions, the model is evaluated with dropout layers forced into training mode while Batch Normalization layers remain in inference mode, preventing running statistics distortion on single-sample inputs. The j -th stochastic forward pass is computed as:

$$\mathcal{P}^{(j)} = \text{Model}(X, \text{dropout}=\text{active}, \text{BN}=\text{inference}) \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (7)$$

In Keras, this is implemented by calling the model with `training=True` on Dropout layers and `training=False` on Batch Normalization layers via layer-level overrides rather than a single global `training`

flag. We compute the mean prediction μ and prediction variance σ^2 across the N stochastic runs:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \mathcal{P}^{(j)}, \quad \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (\mathcal{P}^{(j)} - \mu)^2 \quad (8)$$

If the mean confidence $\mu_{c^*} \geq 0.98$ and the variance $\sigma_{c^*}^2 \leq 0.05$, the system emits a deterministic decision; otherwise, the wafer is labeled as uncertain (**DEFER**).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Dataset and Setup

The model was trained on a dataset of 541 patch images across 8 classes (clean, crack, edge_defect, open, other, scratch, short, and spot), sampled from the NEU Surface Defect Database [12] — a metal surface defect benchmark — via class relabeling to approximate wafer defect taxonomies. We acknowledge that this adaptation introduces a domain gap relative to actual fab wafer imaging; production deployment would require retraining on fab-specific wafer data. Data was split 75/25 train/test (stratified by class). Thresholds were selected empirically on the training set; the absence of a held-out validation set means thresholds may therefore be optimistically biased toward the training distribution. The test dataset consists of 150 images. Benchmarks were executed on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4050 Laptop GPU (6GB VRAM, Windows 11, CUDA 12.6, TensorRT 10.3 [13], onnxruntime-gpu 1.19.2 [14]).

B. Inference Latency Results

We compared the inference latency of the exported ONNX model. TensorRT compiling with FP16 precision achieved significant speedup, as shown in Table I. Latency statistics were computed over $N = 500$ runs after 50 warm-up iterations.

TABLE I
INFERENCE LATENCY ACROSS EXECUTION PROVIDERS (TIMES IN MS)

Provider	Mean	Med.	P95	P99	FPS
CPU Baseline	2.64 ± 0.12	2.46	3.12	3.72	379.1
CUDA	2.74 ± 0.45	2.33	4.01	6.38	364.8
TensorRT FP16	0.79 ± 0.03	0.80	1.05	1.17	1262.2

FP16 quantization introduces $< 0.1\%$ classification accuracy delta compared to the FP32 baseline, verified on the 150-image test set.

C. End-to-End Pipeline Latency

We profiled the entire pipeline latency (from image availability to decision output) comparing a standard file-based pipeline with the OPTI-FAB stream pipeline under TensorRT FP16 acceleration. The file-based baseline uses PNG write → OS fsync → PNG read → decode → GPU transfer on the NVMe SSD. Mean write+read overhead accounts for 5.30 ms of the 8.30 ms total. Latency statistics were computed over $N = 100$ iterations.

TABLE II
END-TO-END PIPELINE LATENCY COMPARISON

Metric	File-Based	OPTI-FAB
Mean Latency	8.30 ± 0.85 ms	3.00 ± 0.32 ms
Median Latency	7.74 ms	2.47 ms
P95 Latency	11.41 ms	4.83 ms
Min Latency	6.27 ms	2.02 ms
Throughput	120.5 fps	333.3 fps
MC Dropout (5 passes)	N/A	24.8 ± 1.2 ms

OPTI-FAB reduces mean pipeline latency by 63.9% (from 8.30 ms to 3.00 ms). The sequential MC Dropout path takes 24.8 ms (Table II) under ‘tf.function’ compilation.

D. Classification Performance

OPTI-FAB achieved an overall baseline accuracy of **91%** on full-frame test images. The per-class evaluation is detailed in Table III.

TABLE III
PER-CLASS EVALUATION METRICS

Defect Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
clean	0.91	1.00	0.95	20
crack	0.95	1.00	0.98	20
edge_defect	0.67	1.00	0.80	20
open	1.00	1.00	1.00	15
other	1.00	0.50	0.67	20
scratch	1.00	1.00	1.00	20
short	1.00	1.00	1.00	15
spot	1.00	0.85	0.92	20
Accuracy			0.91	150

The lower recall on *other* is due to confusion with the *edge_defect* class (Table IV).

TABLE IV
BASELINE FULL-FRAME CONFUSION MATRIX

	cln	crk	edg	opn	oth	scr	sht	spt
clean	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
crack	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0
edge_def	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0
open	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0
other	0	0	10	0	10	0	0	0
scratch	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0
short	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0
spot	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	17

E. Streaming Early Exit Analysis

On the 150-image test set, 92.0% of frames triggered an early exit (mean scan completion at 59.7%), with the remaining 8.0% requiring full-frame inference.

V. DISCUSSION AND FACTORY INTEGRATION

OPTI-FAB achieves a mean pipeline latency of 3.00 ms, meeting the target budget of $T_{\text{budget}} = 3.0$ ms at the median (2.47 ms). Under median conditions, the wafer travels 0.25 mm during the inspection cycle compared to 0.77 mm for

TABLE V
ABLATION OF CONFIDENCE AND ENTROPY THRESHOLDS

Conf.	Entropy	Accuracy	Exit Rate	Mean Scan
0.85	0.35	47.3%	100.0%	53.7%
0.90	0.20	48.7%	100.0%	54.3%
0.95	0.10	51.3%	100.0%	57.3%
0.98	0.05	53.3%	92.0%	59.7%
0.99	0.02	56.0%	80.7%	59.6%

the file-based pipeline, making inline mechanical rejection feasible. However, the P95 latency of 4.83 ms indicates that approximately 5% of frames exceed the budget under GPU scheduling variance, causing these wafers to travel up to 0.48 mm — past the nominal 0.30 mm reject target window. These frames must be handled by a secondary offline inspection path. Hardware interrupt pinning and CUDA stream prioritization are identified as mitigation paths toward consistent sub-3.0 ms latency in production.

Early-exit inference on partially scanned frames triggers at a mean scan completion of 59.7% for 92.0% of frames (Table V). However, because the classification model is trained on full-frame images, the presence of unscanned black buffer regions behaves as an out-of-distribution feature, degrading classification accuracy to 53.3% during early streaming ticks. To achieve production-ready accuracy, future work must incorporate partial-frame data augmentation during training to regularize the model against unscanned buffer regions. The sequential MC Dropout path (24.8 ms) runs in a secondary thread, allowing out-of-band validation for deferred wafers.

A. Limitations

The current evaluation dataset (541 training, 150 test samples) is limited in scale. Production deployment would require retraining on fab-specific data at 10,000+ samples per class. Results presented here demonstrate proof-of-concept feasibility.

VI. CONCLUSION

OPTI-FAB demonstrates that wafer quality control can be optimized as a real-time systems problem. By integrating stream-aware pixel processing, early exits via Shannon entropy, and Laptop GPU TensorRT compilation, the system breaks the file I/O bottleneck. Embedded deployment on Jetson Orin or NXP i.MX8 is reserved for future hardware-in-the-loop validation.

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